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“A LIFELONG PROCESS”

Poverty is the number one, if not, one of the major problems in the world today. In fact, terrible things that are happening now, because of that ‘deprivation of life’ as they always say, are not new to us. We can see people in the streets, mostly children with worn-out clothes begging for food, sleeping in the street corners at night without minding the cold, dank and dirty surrounding, families of large number sharing one piece of fish in a meal, and people vending in the streets or even in bus and train stations despite of the scorching heat of the sun just to earn money. And worst case, poverty leads to prostitution, crime and corruption which also slowly break and bring down the economy of one's nation.

In every edge and corner of the world, some are suffering and fighting for life, but, accept it or not, some are enjoying with their riches, some are valued because of their power, some are enjoying the benefits of their work and some savors their time in relaxing and swimming in big infinity pools with a glass of margarita- all indicate that they were provided with good education!

Knowledge is power! Yes, it is! We become powerful, popular and wealthy because we carry the most important weapon of life, and that is the great knowledge that we obtain through educating ourselves in all aspects of life. Even on simple things, it plays a very important role. Reading the ‘Government Warning’ on cigar box, detaching posters on ‘Post No Bill’ walls, walking on pathways not on the grass with ‘Keep Off the Grass’ sign, or giving importance to signs like ‘Off Limits’, ‘Turn Off the Lights After Using’ and ‘Flush the Toilet Bowl After Using’ are some of the good outputs of educating ourselves.

Education teaches us how to think things wisely with no one is getting hurt. It teaches us how to see the right picture of our future. It enables us to hear every side of the issues and act on things properly. It also teaches us the basic what, when and why. It corrects us if something is immoral or inappropriate and guides us to the right path. It builds our character, enlightens our minds, develops our confidence, respect, integrity and trust not only to ourselves but to others and covers up our fears and weaknesses. All these things abolish hunger and poverty and help us reach the pedestal of success.

We may think that obtaining it means hardships, but that's how it works. We need to sacrifice and suffer in order for us to learn and earn big things in the end. Waking up early and sleeping late at night is just nothing when we begin to enjoy the luxury of life.

Lastly, education helps us become better and useful persons of the society. It is not only about the books, papers and pens but education is also about the lessons of life. It does not end here...it is a lifelong process!

